

Submission to the Call for Evidence

June 25, 2026

Review of the Copyright in the Digital Single Market Directive. Initiative for a better Copyright Environment for European Creativity and Innovation

Directive 2019/790/EU has significantly simplified the use of copyrighted works in teaching contexts and for text and data mining (TDM). In particular, the uniform applicability of mandatory exceptions provides legal certainty in a cross-border context. Furthermore, the express primacy of statutory exceptions over contractual agreements strengthens the bargaining position for research organisations and individual researchers. However, the implementation of the Directive into German law – and into the national laws of other Member States – still leaves a considerable risk of legal action. The resulting fear of litigation may have a chilling effect on researchers, research organisations, and cultural heritage institutions. Consequently, the practical effectiveness of the existing provisions remains impaired by legal uncertainty. Furthermore, unlike teaching, core elements of the research process are still justified under the optional exemptions of Directive 2001/29/EC, which are implemented differently in the member states, thus hindering cross-border cooperation.

A. Definition of “Research Organisation”, “Research” and “Non-Commercial”

Under the current framework, Article 2(1) Directive 2019/790/EU and Article 5(3) Directive 2001/29/EC are shaped by the definitions of “research”, “research organisation” and “non-commercial” conduct. Yet, the interpretation of these concepts still varies considerably between Member States, which burdens cross-border research and may create a chilling effect. This is particularly evident in contract negotiations, where rightsholders frequently adopt a restrictive stance.

To enable researchers and research organisations to make effective use of the existing exceptions, these definitions should be uniform across all jurisdictions and aligned throughout European legislation dealing with copyright and, where possible, adjacent areas such as data protection law.

- a. The current framework grants a broad exception for TDM for scientific research where it is conducted **“by” research organisations and cultural heritage institutions**. Individual researchers and research groups working across multiple organisations are not expressly mentioned. Their activities are currently only covered by the general exceptions in Article 5(3)(a) and (n) Directive 2001/29/EC. This gives rise to legal uncertainty where research is not conducted under the direct responsibility of an institution, but by its members acting independently.

German law therefore extends the TDM exception to **individual researchers**, thereby considering their individual freedom of research. A comparable clarification appears necessary at European level.

- b. An appropriate definition of “**research**” is essential to ensure the free cross-border flow of ideas. It should clearly distinguish purely private use from privileged activities of members and accredited users of research institutions, including early-career researchers. The definition should be aligned with the drafts of the Digital Omnibus to avoid divergent treatment of sources used for text and data mining under copyright and data protection law. The definition of research should be functional rather than exclusively status- or institution-based. It should also encompass research-based and inquiry-based learning, student research projects, doctoral and other qualification research, provided that these activities follow recognised academic standards and are carried out within or in connection with a research or higher education institution.
- c. The definition of “**research organisation**” should correspond closely to the concept used in the General Block Exemption Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 651/2014). This would promote uniform interpretation and help prevent unduly restrictive readings at national level. The definition should be aligned with, but not necessarily limited to, the concept of a research and knowledge-dissemination organisation under the General Block Exemption Regulation and should fully reflect the specific functions of higher education institutions.
- d. A clear and workable definition of “**non-commercial**” research is indispensable. Article 2 Directive 2019/790/EU already provides some legal certainty with respect to privately funded university research. However, it should be clarified what constitutes a “decisive influence” of a private undertaking on scientific research. Moreover, it remains unclear to what extent commercial follow-on uses of results of text and data mining (e.g. AI models) originally conducted for non-commercial research are covered by Article 3 Directive 2019/790/EU. Subsequent commercial exploitation of research results should not retroactively affect the lawfulness of text and data mining originally carried out for non-commercial scientific research.

B. Licensing and Enforcement of Copyright and Related Rights in the AI context

Neither the exception for non-commercial research in Article 3 nor the general TDM exception in Article 4 Directive 2019/790/EU currently requires compensation; this follows explicitly from Recital 17 Directive 2019/790/EU. While the interests of rightsholders are understandable, any compensation scheme must take account of its effects on competition and its differentiated impact on specific categories of rightsholders. In particular, rules on remuneration must not impede AI research and its application in the research sector, nor restrict access to such technologies to a small group of private actors able to pay high licence fees.

- a. Requiring compensation for TDM conducted for non-commercial research would, in practice, prevent such activities. The ability to mine licensed or publicly available content is essential not only in computer science but also in the social sciences, in the digital humanities and health research. Ex ante licensing would prevent fundamental research and confine the benefit of the exception to a few specially funded research projects. To balance interests, legislation should instead focus on regulating the use of data obtained under the research exception rather than the act of mining itself.
- b. Restricting accessible content for TDM to works specifically registered by rightsholders in a central registry is not a viable solution for scientific research. An opt-in model would drastically reduce the scope of accessible works and thus prevent the creation of neutral and representative corpora and models. This would not only reduce efficiency, but also risk bias, misalignment, and ineffective models.

- c. If compensation for (commercial) TDM were to be introduced, it should be limited to **flat-fee collective licensing mechanisms** to avoid disproportionate transaction costs in identifying and negotiating with individual rightsholders. Otherwise, crawling and data mining for research purposes would become impossible, for instance where the relevant rightsholders in film clips or public-internet content cannot realistically be identified. Article 12 Directive 2019/790/EU should be extended to facilitate simple, efficient licensing for any interested party.

C. Scope of the TDM-Exemption

While the mandatory rule in Article 3 Directive 2019/790/EU has significantly increased legal certainty in the use of digital technologies when dealing with copyrighted works, certain activities continue to fall under the optional general exception in Article 5(3) Directive 2001/29/EC.

- a. The wording of Articles 3 and 4 Directive 2019/790/EU should be amended expressly to clarify that **creation and training of AI models** constitute “text and data mining” within the meaning of these provisions. The current legal debate on this point creates uncertainty and may have a chilling effect on innovative research.
- b. Article 3 Directive 2019/790/EU should be extended explicitly to cover **review processes, archiving and re-use of research results and research data** obtained through TDM. At present, the wording is limited to the TDM process as such and does not expressly include review procedures that are essential to scientific research. Proper review often requires making training data accessible to third parties. This has been expressly allowed by the German legislator under Article 5(3)(a) Directive 2001/29/EC. However, not all Member States provide an exception permitting third-party access to mined content. This impedes sound scientific practice in an international context.
- c. A new exception should permit the **use of copyrighted content in AI systems for research purposes**. Articles 3 and 4 Directive 2019/790/EU currently cover TDM for training models, but they do not clearly allow researchers to use AI systems on copyrighted works to produce research results, for example through translation, summarisation or analysis of texts or other data. These uses are typically classified as adaptations under national copyright laws yet are not expressly regulated in EU copyright law.

Since many widely used AI systems cannot be run locally, reliance on third-party systems hosted on external infrastructure is often indispensable. If such systems do not use input data for further training, right holders are no more affected than when researchers use local tools. The use of third-party AI systems for research purposes should be permitted where appropriate technical and contractual safeguards ensure purpose limitation, confidentiality, access control, non-reuse for model training and deletion of input data.

D. Exception for Scientific Research (Article 5(3)(a) Directive 2001/29/EC)

As demonstrated in the study accompanying the ERA Action (<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/77395a15-133b-11ef-a251-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>, pp. 146 et seq.), Member States have made vastly different use of the optional research exception in Article 5(3)(a) Directive 2001/29/EC. In Germany, for example, making works available within research groups is limited to 15%, and a

researcher may not copy more than 75% of a work for individual research (Section 60c UrhG). By contrast, some Member States allow unlimited reproduction for individual non-commercial research and do not restrict sharing within small groups of named researchers.

These divergences create liability risks and legal uncertainty in cross-border research cooperation. Harmonised rules would foster collaboration, ensure competitiveness of research across the Union, and broaden the pool of available works.

- a. While Article 5 Directive 2019/790/EU introduces a **mandatory exception** “for the sole purpose of illustration for teaching”, no analogous obligatory rule exists under Directive 2001/29/EC for “research”. The mere optional nature of Article 5(3)(a) hampers cross-border cooperation and researcher mobility and weakens the competitive position of European research.
- b. An appropriate research exception must not be confined to the early stages of research, such as the collection of existing works, but should extend to the **entire research lifecycle**. This includes review, publication of results, documentation of research data and outputs, as well as follow-up projects. The mandatory exception should not be limited to sharing content within small research groups – which will often not even qualify as “public” communication – but should also cover the reproduction and sharing of articles in a broader context. As far as possible, full harmonisation, including clear rules on quantities that may be reproduced and shared, is essential for a level playing field and for effective cross-border cooperation.
- c. To prevent publishers from contractually neutralising research exceptions, **clear rules on applicable law and on the relationship between statutory exceptions and contractual terms** are required. Unlike the cross-border teaching exception in Article 5 Directive 2019/790/EU – which expressly overrides contractual agreements and is supported by a specific conflict-of-law rule (Article 5(3): “shall be deemed to occur solely in the Member State where the educational establishment is established”) – there is no comparable regime for cross-border research. Extending these rules mutatis mutandis to research activities not tied to a single hosting institution could, however, trigger forum shopping. This risk must be addressed by carefully designed conflict-of-law provisions.

E. Exception for Digital Libraries (Article 5(3)(n) Directive 2001/29/EC)

Libraries may make works from their collections available to researchers under the optional exception in Article 5(3)(n) Directive 2001/29/EC, which has been implemented, for example, in German law. However, the scope of this provision no longer corresponds to current standards and needs of digital research. In practice, the rule has little relevance because it is limited to “dedicated terminals on the premises of establishments”, which often does not even include researchers’ offices outside the library.

- a. In contrast to Article 5 Directive 2019/790/EU, there is no express provision **preventing contractual agreements from overriding the library exception**. German law does provide such a rule, but only for contracts concluded after 1 March 2018 (Section 137o UrhG), leaving earlier – and often perpetual or long-term – agreements unaffected. To ensure legal certainty, EU law should provide for a uniform and mandatory exception that clearly prevails over any contractual terms, including those in existing agreements.
- b. The limitation to “dedicated terminals **on the premises**” hampers modern access to knowledge and prevents full exploitation of digital collections. The exception should be

extended to encompass “a secure electronic environment accessible only to authorised users”, as already foreseen for teaching in Article 5 Directive 2019/790/EU. In times of virtual private networks, such a solution would provide an infrastructure that genuinely supports digital research.

- c. Libraries also require clear and binding exceptions enabling them to **preserve materials** to which they legitimately have access, including works accessed under licence and works freely available on the internet. At present, such preservation exceptions are optional and diverge across Member States. Much like the exemption for teaching in Article 5 Directive 2019/790/EU, uniform rules are needed to ensure effective cross-border cooperation.

F. Sharing, Accessing and Re-Using the Results of Publicly Funded Research

The German secondary publication right (Section 38(4) UrhG, introduced in 2014) has had limited impact on the overall number of open-access publications (see the Economic analysis of options for improving EU legislative and regulatory frameworks with impact on access and reuse of publicly funded R&I results and of publications and data for scientific purposes – Final report, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8969719>). A future European regulatory framework should avoid the pitfalls of the German model and be closely aligned with actual research practices. Legal certainty – particularly the overriding effect of statutory rights vis-à-vis contractual provisions – must be at its core.

- a. The current German provision **lacks legal clarity**. The requirement that research must be at least 50% funded from “public funds” is often interpreted as referring solely to additional public project funding, thereby excluding publicly funded institutional running costs. Moreover, the right applies only to specific types of publications (works in periodicals published at least twice a year) and subsequent re-use. This legal uncertainty can expose individual researchers to personal liability and reputational risk, which they will naturally seek to avoid.
- b. Although the statutory right formally overrides contractual limitations, German researchers still fear de facto **repercussions by publishers in future projects** if they rely unilaterally on their secondary publication right. In works with multiple authors, all authors must agree to exercise the right, which makes its use cumbersome and often impracticable.
- c. In some research fields, a one-year **embargo period** is perceived as excessively long, as it may render the publication irrelevant for the respective community by the time Open Access becomes possible. Embargo periods should therefore be tailored to the specific dynamics of different disciplines; a uniform rule is unlikely to be appropriate.
- d. The liability of institutions operating repositories should be limited. A European framework should provide a uniform notice-and-takedown mechanism with appropriate review procedures. Liability for damages should be confined to intentional infringements or, at a minimum, to cases where the provider had prior knowledge of the copyright infringement.

Even if the direct effect of secondary publication rights on individual authors cannot always be demonstrated empirically, the introduction of Section 38(4) UrhG has strengthened the bargaining position of authors and institutions in negotiations with publishers. Thus, even where individual researchers do not exercise the right and institutions cannot directly influence their decision, its mere existence provides leverage that indirectly promotes Open Access.

G. Chilling Effect of Potential Liability and Unfair Contract Terms

The mere threat of litigation and liability discourages libraries and research organisations from relying on statutory exceptions. Both institutions and individual researchers should therefore be exempt from damages and criminal liability where they **act with due care**, based on reasonable judgement and in good faith when accessing copyrighted content. This liability privilege should be supported by a conflict-of-law rule ensuring that, in cross-border research cooperation, no stricter standards apply than those in the jurisdiction of the research organisation (or researcher). Researchers and research organisations acting in good faith, with due care and within institutionally approved procedures should not be personally liable for damages in cases of minor or excusable infringements.

In addition, **unfair – and even legally invalid – contractual terms** imposed by rightsholders which limit or exclude statutory exceptions (for example under Article 3 Directive 2019/790/EU) remain widespread. Because research organisations and libraries depend on access to content and often have weak bargaining power, robust safeguards and easily accessible review procedures are required. Comparable to consumers under Directive 93/13/EEC, research organisations and individual researchers should enjoy special protection against unfair contractual terms.

The Alliance of Science Organisations is an association of the most significant science organisations in Germany. It regularly comments on important issues of science policy. The Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft is a member of the Alliance and has taken on the role of spokesperson for 2025. Other members are the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation, the German Academic Exchange Service, the German Research Foundation, the Helmholtz Association of German Research Centers, the German Rectors' Conference, the Leibniz Association, the Max Planck Society, the German National Academy of Sciences Leopoldina and the German Science and Humanities Council.

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